
THE NATURE OF CONFLICT IN PLATEAU NORTH SENATORIAL DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

The Plateau state known for its peaceful nature and blessed with unique geographical features has in recent years been described as a theater of recurrent violent eruption accompanied by massive displacement of population with impact on household livelihood of the victims. The primary objective of this study is to examine the nature of conflict in Plateau North Senatorial District. This study adopted the descriptive cross-sectional survey design. It employed the mixed-methods approach where primary data were obtained through structured questionnaires, Key Informant Interview (KII) and In-depth Interviews among the local government areas of Barkin-Ladi, Bassa and Riyom. In obtaining the data, 380 questionnaires administered to participants, nine key informants were drawn from the study population for the key informant interview (KII) and ten individuals comprising of household's heads including those headed by females were selected for the in-depth interviews. The preliminary data were analyzed using the descriptive statistics with the computer software of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. The findings of the study revealed the nature of violent conflicts in Plateau North Senatorial District to be categorized into religious-based conflict, ethnic-based conflict, political-based conflict and resource-based conflict. The study offers some recommendations including the following: Resolving historical grievances; Dialogue and mediation program; boundary demarcations farmers and herders; and a tougher justice system.

KEYWORDS: Nature of Conflicts, Violence, Plateau North Senatorial District

INTRODUCTION

Conflict is a common occurrence which cannot be avoided in most human relationships. It manifests itself in different degrees and dimensions at every human life or social context. Even though conflict has a potential cost, not all conflicts result in negative outcome especially when properly managed. Conflict becomes violent when it results to loss of lives and destruction of property. Conflict can be between individuals or groups with different personalities. It arises when one perceives threat to its goal, accomplishments or existence by the other party.

Plateau North Senatorial District for some decades has been trapped in a cycle of violent conflicts with great implicit on the lives, property and development in the area. The state once known for its peaceful nature was tuned into a theater or stage of recurrent violent conflicts. The beautiful geographical features, favorable weather and fertile land of Plateau attracted people to the State. The discovery of Tin and columbite deposits attracted quite a number of laborers during the colonial era (Dalyop & Yaob, 2018). Moreover, the land favors the production of crops as well as livestock production which attracted headers from all over the northern region. Plateau North Senatorial District is characterized by diverse ethnic and religious groups that once existed in peace and harmony, which is now, threaten by the violent conflict that erupted in the state. Consequently, various forms of violent conflict were experienced which include the indigene/settles conflicts, ethno-religious conflicts, political conflicts and farmer/herders conflicts the attack is mostly in the rural villages of the senatorial district.

Plateau North Senatorial District comprises six local government areas namely: Jos-North, Jos-South, Jos-East, Barkin-Ladi, Bassa and Riyom. This area is inhabited by the indigenous people which are the Berom, Afizere, Anaguta, Bache (Rukuba), Irigwe, Buji and the Hausas who are regarded the non -indigenesor settlers. This area had been involved in a cycle of violent conflict which was initially between the BAA and the Hausas, but recently there has been various clash between the farmers and the Fulani herders in the surrounding villages. The violent conflict has caused loss of lives, destruction of property, displacement of people with effect to the development of the state must especially plateau North Senatorial District.

Based on the above account, violent conflict has become a recurrent and disturbing occurrence in Nigeria which affects every state in one way or the other. The violent conflicts range from religious, political, indigenes/settlers clash and farmers/herders' clashes. These violent conflicts are responsible for the death of thousands and destructions of property worth billions of naira in the region (Gofwen 2011, Suleiman, 2011). Plateau North Senatorial District has experienced cycle of violent conflicts that have affected the peaceful co-existence of the various ethnic and religious groups that labored and enjoyed relationships. It is against the foregoing background that this paper seeks to understand the nature of conflict in Plateau North Senatorial District.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Conflict

The concept of conflict is defined from different directions by many scholars. It is a reality that exists in everyone's life that is considered as a part of natural process that occurs daily. Conflict usually emerges or surface as a clash of interest or ideas that exist within individual, group or groups that manifest in different forms that includes disagreement anger, quarrel, hatred, destruction, killing or war. Conflict is the fight and competition for things that people and groups value (Adetoye & Omilusi, 2015). When an individual or group attach value to

any object, any threat to it will definitely give rise to conflict as the individual or group will improvise a means of protecting it.

Furthermore, Jeong (2000) Conflict is characterized as a battle between two or more groups over claims, position, control, and resources with the aim of destabilizing the other group that may result to injury or even eliminating them. It can be said to be any mechanism in which individuals and groups goals and aspiration are achieved. When attitudes or actions that are capable of causing change in the social, or political environment are employ, is likely to evolve into conflict. These attitudes are greed, self-centeredness, covetousness', discontent, envy, arrogance, rudeness, impurity, among others.

Conflict can be as a result of disagreement between two or more individuals or groups, with each individual or group struggling to gain control or acceptance of its objectives or views. Nicholson (1992) noted that conflict is any act that an individual or group will employ as a means of achieving its wants, needs, or obligations. It may involve disagreement when the parties involved perceive a threat to their needs, interest, or concerns. This shows that the individuals or groups don't have the same views on the same issue. Individuals, or groups always have different goals which is evident in the struggle for position and power in the society involving two or more actors opposing each other in interaction and exerting power in an effort to gain control or to attain the goals with strategies to prevent the opponent from attaining same. Violent conflict is a "conflict that involves two parties using physical force to resolve competing claims or interest". (Fre're & Wilen, 2015).

The Nature of Conflict

To understand the nature of conflict, it is important to examine the classification of parties involved. These parties can be categorized into social groups, individuals, communities, ethnic groups, nations, states, and regions. This classification highlights significant differences in levels of organization and the nature of differences that exist within and among these categories. As a result, conflicts may vary based on the ideologies of the involved parties, and the behaviour exhibited during conflict may not follow a consistent pattern. Each party in a conflict typically develops its own strategies and processes to pursue its goals. In any conflict, there is usually a primary party, which represents the main opposing force. These primary parties are directly engaged in the conflict and stand to gain or lose the most from its outcome. Secondary parties, on the other hand, are typically allies or sympathizers of the primary parties. While they support the conflict in some way, they do not usually benefit directly from its outcome (Burgess, 2017).

Conflict can be classified base on the actors involved in the conflict and the location. These categories lack clarity because of the foreign involvement in internal conflicts, which makes it difficult to distinguish between national and international conflicts. Example of such is the case of the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), the war that started as national was later referred to as the "first African world war" due to the international intervention (Fre're & Wilen, 2015). The nature of conflict can be viewed or explain in another dimension which is as "a process of polarization and receding opportunity when conflict involve two or more parties, they characteristically move to opposing sides of the issue, which strengthen the case creating gap between them. The conflict further escalates and they resolve in defending their position and destroying the opponents. It is a process that was simple and the reasons was ignore, views and justification of the other side were dismissed. The other party feels they are right while the opponents are wrong (Bowman, 2000).

Conflict can be classified based on the actors involved and the geographical location in which it occurs. However, these categories are not always clearly defined, particularly when distinguishing between national and international conflicts. This is due to the increasing involvement of international actors in what are initially internal conflicts. A notable example is the case of the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), where a conflict that began as a domestic issue later escalated into what has been referred to as the First African World War due to the extensive international intervention (Frère & Wilén, 2015).

The nature of conflict can also be understood as a process of polarization and diminishing opportunities. When a conflict involves two or more parties, they typically adopt opposing stances, which reinforces divisions and widens the gap between them. As the conflict escalates, each side becomes more entrenched in its position, aiming to defend its stance while undermining the opponent. What may have begun as a relatively simple disagreement becomes more complex as the underlying reasons are ignored, and each side dismisses the views and justifications of the other. In such situations, both parties tend to believe they are right and view the other as entirely wrong (Bowman, 2000).

Arbath et al. (2015) conducted a study on the nature of conflict in Africa. The study traced the nature of conflict to be associated to the long exploitation across the continent. Analysis of the study included the genetic diversity of a contemporary national population which was primarily determined over the course of the “out of Africa” expansion of anatomically modern humans. The results show that genetic diversity plays a major role in the degree of polarization and fractionalization among ethnic, linguistic, and religious groups in the country; that genetic diversity has a negative impact on interpersonal trust and cooperation; that genetic diversity contributes to differences in preferences for public goods and redistributive policies; and that genetic diversity may have an effect on economic inequality in a society. The study further revealed that this has contributed significantly to the frequent incident of ethnic civil conflict in society over the last half-century. It also established the power of genetic diversity for the intensity of social unrest and inter-group factual conflict.

Nwagwu (2016) investigated indigene and settlers’ conflict in Nigeria: A negation to national integration and national building. The main objective of the study was to investigate the root causes of intra/inter-communal conflicts which revolves around indigene and settlers’ rivalries with impact on the growth and development of the nation which depends on the harmonious co-existence of all the tribes irrespective of religion, ethnicity or political affiliation. A qualitative research design was used and content analysis was applied in the data analysis. The findings revealed that the unequal redistribution of society benefits and unhealthy struggle for scarce economic resources, cultural heritage syndrome and distrust are responsible for indigene claim and settlers’ discrimination. It further suggests the need for Nigeria people to live together in peace, harmony and harness the abundant resources for the development of the country.

The Nature of Recurrent Violent Conflict in Plateau North Senatorial District

The cycle of violent conflict experienced in Plateau North Senatorial District can be explained in two dimensions which are identity-based conflict and resource-based conflict (Wika, 2014). The pattern of administration inherited from the colonial masters was a divided nation. The Hausa ethnic group in the North, the Yoruba ethnic group to the West, and the Igbo ethnic group to the East while the other minorities within the Middle-Belt and the Niger-Delta regions (Ajayi, 2022). The system is responsible for the ethnic division and also the identity awareness. The notion of federal character was built on this system that paved way

for the ethnic cleavages into the political and economic sectors leading to competition, relevance and group survival.

The cycle of violent conflict experienced in the Plateau North Senatorial District can be explained along two major dimensions: identity-based conflict and resource-based conflict (Wika, 2014). The pattern of governance inherited from colonial rule contributed to a deeply divided nation, with the Hausa ethnic group dominant in the North, the Yoruba in the West, and the Igbo in the East, while minority groups occupied the Middle Belt and Niger Delta regions (Ajayi, 2022). This colonial administrative structure played a significant role in fostering ethnic divisions and identity consciousness. The concept of federal character, which was later introduced, built upon this foundation and further entrenched ethnic cleavages within the political and economic spheres. As a result, it fuelled competition among groups for political relevance and access to resources, reinforcing ethnic loyalty and the struggle for group survival.

In a study conducted by Agbiboa (2017), asserts that the colonial system of government strengthens the differences, solidifying religious and ethnic identity as salient political distinctions responsible for persistent instability. The recurring violent conflicts in Plateau state most especially the northern senatorial district can be traced back to the cold war that existed in the struggles of political power and economic control between the indigenous people and the settlers. The Berom, Afizere, Anaguta, Bache, Buji and Irigwe are considered to be the indigenous people while the Hausa-Fulani considered to be the settlers. The grievances that existed between the individual groups and communities for several decades was transformed into an organized violence in 2001 with each group having the opportunity of expressing its dissatisfaction and frustration as regard to political and economic marginalization. This has led to increased sense of intolerance, fear and suspicious across several ethno-religious and communal divides (Plateau Peace Building Agency 2018; Cingel & Ugwoke, 2019). The conflict among the indigenes and the Settlers who both are the present inhabitants is as a result of cold war under the “ownership” of Jos land. The issue was long neglected, ignored and not attended to or resolved. The settlers or immigrants are holding claim to the land due to prolong stay and contributions to the development and growth of the area (Okechukwu, 2016). The competition between the indigenous people and the non-indigenous people or settlers to gain control over the scarce resources have been responsible for the recurrent violent conflicts.

Agbiboa (2017) asserts that the colonial system of government reinforced societal divisions by solidifying religious and ethnic identities as key political distinctions, thereby contributing to persistent instability. The recurring violent conflicts in Plateau State—particularly in the Northern Senatorial District—can be traced to longstanding tensions rooted in the struggle for political power and economic control between indigenous populations and settler communities. The Berom, Afizere, Anaguta, Bache, Buji, and Irigwe are considered indigenous to the area, whereas the Hausa-Fulani are regarded as settlers. Decades of grievances between these groups gradually escalated and culminated in organized violence in 2001, offering each group an outlet to express dissatisfaction and frustration over political and economic marginalization. This has led to heightened intolerance, fear, and mutual suspicion across various ethno-religious and communal divides (Plateau Peace Building Agency, 2018; Cingel & Ugwoke, 2019).

The conflict between indigenous groups and settlers—both of whom are current residents—centres on the contentious issue of land ownership in Jos. This underlying dispute, long ignored and unresolved, has deepened over time. Settlers claim ownership based on

prolonged residence and significant contributions to the area's development (Okechukwu, 2016). Ultimately, the competition for control over scarce resources between indigenous and non-indigenous groups has been a major driver of recurring violent conflict in the region.

Indigenes and Settlers

Indigenous peoples are culturally and socially distinct ethnic groups who maintain shared access to natural resources and ancestral connections to the lands they have either been displaced from or continue to inhabit. They uphold and pass down unique cultural traditions and sustain a deep relationship with both their environment and their communities (Rademacher, 2023). As defined by Reyes-García et al. (2018), Indigenous peoples are ethnic groups who are descended from and identify with the original inhabitants of a given region.

The dichotomy between indigenes and non-indigenes has been created in section 318(1) of the Nigeria constitution of 1999 (as amended). An indigene is defined as a person belonging to a state whose parents or whose any grandparent was a member of a community indigenous to the state; section 15(3)b of the constitution stated that, it is the duty of the state to “secure full residence rights for every citizen on all parts of the Federation.” The constitution failed to specify the rights of Nigerian citizens who are born or reside outside their ancestral states of origin. Two critical problems that have been persistent on the status of indigenes and non-indigenes are: (a) Eligibility of non-indigenes for election into public office within the states, and (b) equal access by indigenes and non-indigenes to services and opportunities provided by the state and local government. This gap has been the source of contention between the indigenes and non-indigenes in most communities which often explodes into violent conflict. The indigenes – settlers’ dichotomy has become a recurring decimal within Nigeria, the cleavages on religion, culture and language have been a major contribution to the dichotomy. A unique characteristic of the indigene settler dichotomy is the indigenous inclusiveness and the settler’s exclusiveness as a result of the primordially defined boundaries and border (Olakunle et al., 2016).

Karakoc and Wang (2021) conducted a global study on minorities, ethnic conflicts, and public confidence in the United Nations (UN). The study aimed to explore the extent to which minorities differ from majorities in their trust in the UN, particularly in countries that have experienced ethnic conflict. It focused on the conditions under which minorities tend to place greater confidence in the UN’s role and involvement. Using data from the World Values Survey collected between 1981 and 2012, the researchers found that political regimes significantly influence the trust gap between minorities and majorities. The results also indicated that increased confidence in the UN among minority groups may contribute to the persistence of ethnic conflicts.

In France, Zhang (2023) conducted a study on the intrinsic conflict within ethnic and religious issues. The study focused on the underlying logic of value claims presented by various ideologies, as well as the practical mechanisms driving conflicts related to ethnic and religious issues in the country. It also explored the historical context of immigration in France, offering insights into the identity crises linked to ethnic and religious diversity. The methodology relied on theoretical discussions, published documents, and research findings from official institutions. The study found that France has historically emphasized its identity as a political community. Over time, the concept of a “civic nation” gained prominence, while the idea of an “ethnic nation” became increasingly marginalized or stigmatized. Additionally, the growing ethnic diversity in France has led to significant social changes, raising concerns among the indigenous population regarding national and state identity.

However, a key limitation of the study was the lack of a formal research design with systematic data collection and analysis. As a result, the findings cannot be generalized.

Similarly, Belge and Karakoç (2015) conducted a study on minorities in the Middle East: ethnicity, religion, and support for authoritarianism, focusing on Turkey, Egypt, Morocco, and Jordan. The research examined the conditions under which minorities participate in authoritarian systems and form coalitions with majority groups. Using survey data, the study explored how political changes influence minorities' preferences for regime types and how three historical legacies have shaped social and political divisions in the Middle East. These legacies include: (1) the Ottoman-Islamic tradition of minority accommodation, (2) the emergence of an ethnic class structure in the 19th century as a result of religious integration into global markets, and (3) the post-independence pattern of authoritarian secularism. The findings revealed that linguistic minorities tend to show lower levels of support for authoritarian regimes, while religious minorities are more likely to support them.

Elom (2021) conducted a study examining the Nigerian state and the indigene-ship dichotomy, focusing on its challenges and prospects. The study aimed to explore the implications of the indigene-settler divide, issues surrounding citizenship, and constitutional deficiencies that contribute to ongoing crises affecting the rights and privileges of Nigerian citizens. It also assessed the role of the state in addressing and mediating these dilemmas. A descriptive qualitative research design was employed, and content analysis was used to analyze the data. The findings revealed that ethnic political elites have exacerbated the citizenship crisis by promoting tribal and religious sentiments as tools for political and economic mobilization. However, the study was limited by the absence of a clearly defined geographical focus within Nigeria and a lack of detail regarding the data collection strategy, which restricts the generalizability of its findings.

A study was conducted by Anjide and Amaechi (2020) to examine the intractability of violent conflict in Nigeria, a case of Plateau State." The main focus of the study was to examine the dynamics and actors to the recurring conflicts. The study adopted the exploratory research design, non-probability sampling technique and purposive sampling method to select 25 respondents. Data were collected through semi-structured interview. The study found that the root cause of the conflict is anchored on contested citizenship in forms of citizens-settlers debate. It further suggested a three-phase plan to addressing the intractability of the crises which include short-, medium- and long-term plans. The major limitation of the study is in the sample size which made it impossible to be generalized.

Furthermore, Ogbuleke (2019) conducted research on ethno-religious conflict and democracy in Jos, Plateau State (2007–2012). With the goal of presenting a solution for its continuation in Nigeria, the study concentrated on how ethno-religious conflicts impact democracy. Both primary and secondary sources of data were employed, and a descriptive study design was chosen. The results showed that the main reasons of violent disputes in Plateau State are often identity, poverty, unemployment, marginalization, discrimination, lack of political representation, neglect, and elite manipulation..

Similarly, Nyam (2017) conducted a study on Explaining Research Findings on the Conflicts in Jos – Nigeria. This study used a case paper design to explore innovative approaches for repositioning the practice of forum theatre in the context of conflict resolution. A mixed-method approach was employed. The study revealed that conflicts in Jos are rooted in struggles over political, social, economic, religious, and ethnic issues. These conflicts have significantly affected residential patterns, places of worship, and intergroup relations, leading

to new trends in settlement. The study recommended peacebuilding initiatives, public enlightenment campaigns, advocacy efforts, and the integration of segregated communities as potential solutions.

Likewise, Wika (2014) conducted a study on “Unveiling the Salient Issues in the Protracted Jos Crises, Central Nigeria. The study critically examined the causes and content of the protracted crises in Jos Plateau State, Nigeria since 1994. The conflict was traced back to the exploitative and competitive colonial system which was responsible for mass migrates, ethnic-politics and religious contestations. The violent conflict led to the creation of the indigene and settlers’ problems including the Christian and Muslims militias. The study further explained the nature of Jos conflict which are resource and identity based in a contest over the nature, political and economic control of Jos. All attempts to find a lasting solution to the violence was not successful due to the fact that the procedures are politicized.

Based on the above studies the nature of Jos violent conflicts can be narrowed down to identity and recourse-based conflict, which arises from the competition between the indigenous people (Berom, Afizre, Anaguta, Bache, Irigwe, amongst others) and the settlers (Hausa – Fulani). Identity exists always on two levels, which are the “internal identity” and “external identity”. Identity is shaped by recognition from others and not based on self-awareness and belonging. Identity theorist defined it as “a set of meaning that persons use to define who they are in their social categories (categorical identity), group membership (group identity) social roles (role identity), or as unique individuals (person identities) (Aldecoa, 2019). Identity is regarded as a social construct and sets of meaning that defined who we are in terms of the roles we play, social categories or groups we belong or based on the individual unique characteristics possessed.

The root cause of identity violence can be traced Thailand’s crisis to an unresolved struggle which arise from the content of Thailand’s national identity which was dated back to abolition of absolute monarchy in 1932 (Ferrara, 2017). Human history all over the world was driven by a quest for recognition struggle. The dignity of human being has been challenged by the desire for recognition which is universal and the recognition are based on some partial forms which are nation, religion, sect, race, ethnicity, gender, or by individuals who seek to be recognized as superior (Fukuyama, 2018). Similarly in a study by Anthony (2014), identity and citizenship questions in Nigeria: A critical Reflection it traced the root of identity practice to the contradictions inherent in the nation’s constitution. Nigeria is characterized as a divided state which most political issues are violently contested along the lines of ethnic, religious, and regional divisions entangled with political silent identities, intractable conflicts and instability.

Identity usually starts as resistance which became dormant in the institutions of society and therefore becoming legitimizing identities to rationalize their domination. Identities have historically been significant in Nigeria political process from the colonial rule to the post-colonial dispensation. The religious, regional and ethnic differences were given prominence that led to the formulation of certain policies that strengthen the division. The political elites have often used the ethnic and religious sentiments in mobilizing support for selfish gain (Segun et al., 2023).

Based on the above studies, the nature of violent conflict in Jos can be broadly categorized into identity-based and resource-based conflicts. These conflicts stem primarily from competition between the indigenous groups—such as the Berom, Afizere, Anaguta, Bache, and Irigwe—and the settler communities, most notably the Hausa-Fulani. Identity is a key driver in this dynamic and is often expressed on two levels: internal identity (self-awareness

and belonging) and external identity (recognition by others). Identity is not formed in isolation but shaped through societal acknowledgment. As Aldecoa (2019) explains, identity encompasses the meanings individuals assign to themselves based on social categories (categorical identity), group memberships (group identity), social roles (role identity), or unique personal attributes (personal identity). It is essentially a social construct that defines who we are in relation to our social environment.

The root causes of identity-based violence are not unique to Nigeria. For instance, Ferrara (2017) links Thailand's long-standing conflict to an unresolved struggle over national identity that dates back to the abolition of the absolute monarchy in 1932. Globally, history has shown that human conflicts are often fuelled by a quest for recognition. Fukuyama (2018) argues that the universal human desire for dignity and recognition—often filtered through partial forms such as nation, religion, race, ethnicity, gender, or personal superiority—has been a major driver of unrest.

Similarly, Anthony (2014) in the study on identity and citizenship questions in Nigeria: A critical reflection, traces identity-based conflict in Nigeria to contradictions embedded within the nation's constitution. Nigeria is characterized as a deeply divided state, where political issues are often contested violently along ethnic, religious, and regional lines. These divisions are entangled with persistent structural inequalities and intractable conflicts.

Identity, in many cases, begins as a form of resistance but gradually becomes embedded in institutional structures, thereby transforming into legitimizing identities that rationalize existing power hierarchies. Throughout Nigeria's history—from colonialism to the post-colonial era—identity has played a central role in shaping political processes. Colonial policies reinforced religious, regional, and ethnic distinctions, which were later entrenched by post-independence political elites. These elites have continued to exploit identity-based sentiments to mobilize support and advance personal or group interests, often at the expense of national cohesion (Segun et al., 2023).

In this case, the Plateau North Senatorial District can be described as a multi-ethnic society comprising of the indigenous people (BAA) and the non-indigenous people (Hausa-Fulani and others). Each of this group has its unique identity, culture and values that must be protected and threat to any identity can hardly be ignore. The conflict that started in the early 1990s with a deadly turn in 2001 was a clash between the indigenous (BAA) and the settlers (Hausa-Fulani) over the political representation and economic control that turned into ethno-religious and political violence. The recurring violent conflict in the state is as a result of awareness of identity and the struggle over the scarce available resources.

Theoretical Underpinning

The study adopts the frustration aggression theory. The theory can be traced to the works of Dollard et al. (1939). It is a physiological theory which concept explains the cause of aggressive behavior in humans, particularly focusing on aggression that arises from frustration. The theory entails that aggression is as a result of obstruction from reaching a significant goal, which eventually leads to frustration and subsequent aggressive behavior. It explains hostile aggression which occurs when a person is frustrated from achieving a goal and responds with anger and intent to cause pain. Berkowitz (1989) noted that frustrations generate aggressive inclinations only to the extent that they produce negative effect.

The frustration aggression theory is applicable in the recurrent violent conflicts experienced in Plateau North Senatorial District. It can be deduced that the violent conflicts are as a result

of aggression that developed out of frustration from the opposing groups. The parties involved in the violent conflicts are frustrated over the obstruction from reaching or achieving their goals. The frustration and aggressive behavior led to the violent conflict experienced in Plateau North Senatorial District. Aggression can take the form of retaliation on the initial source of frustration or certain situations can constrain the person from reacting on the actual source of the frustration when the person or group is more powerful (Jost & Mentovich, 2017).

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a mixed-methods approach and a cross-sectional survey design to gain an in-depth understanding of the nature of conflict in Plateau North Senatorial District (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The research was conducted in the Plateau North Senatorial District, which comprises six local government areas; however, data were collected from three local government areas—Barkin-Ladi, Bassa, and Riyom—that have experienced the most recurrent violent conflicts. The estimated population figures according to the National Bureau of Statistics 2016 were as follows: Barkin-Ladi – 235,500; Bassa – 248,700; and Riyom – 172,600, resulting in a total population of 656,800 for the quantitative survey. A sample of 380 respondents was selected using Krejcie and Morgan’s (1970) sample size determination table. For the qualitative aspect, data were gathered from 9 key informant interviews (KIIs) and 10 general interview respondents. The survey instruments were adapted, operationalized, and pilot-tested to minimize common method bias. They also met content validity criteria, with a reliability coefficient of 0.678 and above (Tehseen et al., 2017). Data collected from the field were analyzed descriptively and presented in frequencies and percentages using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 26.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio – Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

The findings from the analysis of the socio-demographic attributes of both survey respondents and interview participants are presented in Tables 1–3. The background information provides insights into the composition of the study population. Variables considered include age group, gender, marital status, educational level, religion, occupation, and local government of residence, all of which are relevant to understanding the context of the study.

Table 1

Socio – Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Gender:		
Male	196	58.5
Female	139	41.5
Marital Status:		
Single	88	26.3
Married	198	59.1
Widowed	44	13.1
Divorced	5	1.5
Age Range:		
18-27 years	72	21.5
28-37 years	95	28.4
38-47 years	103	30.7
48-57 years	54	16.1
58 years & above	11	3.3
Religion:		
Christianity	322	91.6
Islam	8	2.4
ATR	5	1.5
Educational Level:		
Non-formal	14	2.4
Primary	20	6.0
Secondary	178	53.1
Tertiary	123	36.7
Occupation:		
Casual worker	46	13.7
Civil servant	36	10.7
Business	91	27.2
Farmer	162	48.4
Local Government:		
Barki Ladi	168	50.1
Bassa	67	11.9
Riyom	127	37.9

The majority of survey participants were male (58.5%), and most were married (59.1%). The predominant age range was 38–47 years (30.7%), followed closely by 28–37 years (28.4%). Christians constituted the majority (91.6%) of the respondents, which reflects the religious demographics of the conflict-affected areas. Over half (53.1%) had secondary education, and a significant portion (36.7%) attained tertiary education. Farming was the dominant

occupation (48.4%), followed by business activities (27.2%). Most respondents resided in Barkin Ladi (50.1%), followed by Riyom (37.9%) and Bassa (11.9%).

Table 2
 Socio-Demographics of Key Interview Informants (KII)

S/N	Sex	Age	Marital status	Educational level	Religion	Occupation	Monthly income	LGA
1	Female	48years	Married	Secondary	Christianity	Farmer	₦40,000	B/Ladi
2	Male	50years	Married	Tertiary	Muslim	Civil servant	₦70,000	B/Ladi
3	Female	40years	Married	Tertiary	Christianity	Farmer	₦60,000	B/Ladi
4	Male	36years	Married	Tertiary	Muslim	Herder	₦30,000	Bassa
5	Male	33years	Married	Tertiary	Christianity	Farmer	₦30,000	Bassa
6	Male	45years	Married	Tertiary	Muslim	Business	₦30,000	Bassa
7	Male	24years	Single	Tertiary	Christianity	Student	-	Riyom
8	Male	53years	Married	Tertiary	Christianity	Civil servant	₦60,000	Riyom
9	Female	47years	Married	Tertiary	Christianity	Civil servant	₦30,000	Riyom

Among the KII participants, 66.7% were male, reflecting the male-dominated nature of leadership roles in traditional and religious institutions. The average age was 43 years. Most were married (88.9%) and educated at tertiary level, although largely at diploma level. Christians made up 66.7% of respondents. Farmers and civil servants each made up 33.3% of the participants. Income ranged between ₦30,000 and ₦70,000, with an average of ₦38,888.89. The representation was evenly distributed across the three LGAs.

Table 3
 Socio-Demographics of In-Depth Interview (IDI) Participants

S/N	Gender	Age	Marital status	Educational level	Religion	Occupation	Monthly income	LGA
1	Female	38-47 years	Married	Tertiary	Christianity	Civil servant	₦30,000	B/Ladi
2	Male	48-57 years	Married	Tertiary	Christianity	Farmer	₦60,000	B/Ladi
3	Female	38-47 years	Widow	Tertiary	Muslim	Trade	₦30,000	B/Ladi
4	Female	28-37 years	Single	Secondary	Christianity	Student	₦10,000	Bassa
5	Female	28-37 years	Married	Non-formal	Muslim	Farmer	₦20,000	Bassa
6	Female	18-27 years	Single	Secondary	Christianity	Farmer	₦20,000	Bassa
7	Male	58-60 years	Married	Secondary	Christianity	Civil servant	₦15,000	Riyom
8	Female	38-47 years	Widow	Primary	Christianity	Farmer	₦20,000	Riyom
9	Male	48-57 years	Married	Tertiary	Christianity	Student	₦30,000	Riyom
10	Male	38-47 years	Single	Secondary	Muslim	Farmer	₦20,000	Riyom

Of the IDI participants, 60% were female, likely due to fewer restrictions on participation in informal roles. The dominant age group was 38–47 years (40%). Half were married, 30% were single, and 20% were widowed. Educational attainment was fairly balanced: 40% each had tertiary and secondary education. Most participants were Christians (70%), and the

dominant occupation was farming (50%), followed by civil service (20%). Monthly income mostly ranged between ₦20,000 and ₦30,000. Participants were drawn from Barkin Ladi (30%), Bassa (30%), and Riyom (40%).

Figure 1: Nature of Violent Conflict Themes

Findings on the Nature of Violent Conflict in Plateau North Senatorial District

Table 4

Nature of Violent Conflicts

Item	SA F (%)	A F (%)	U F (%)	D F (%)	SD F (%)	Total
The violent conflict in Plateau North Senatorial District is executed by both the indigenous/non indigenous militia groups.	28(8.4)	99(29.6)	3(9.0)	191(57.0)	14(4.2)	335
The violent conflict in Plateau North Senatorial District has manifested some elements of group identity.	162(48.4)	154(46.0)	7(2.1)	9(2.7)	3(0.9)	335
The violent conflict in Plateau North Senatorial District can be described as ethnic group violence.	41(12.2)	51(15.2)	138(41.2)	77(23.0)	28(4.2)	335
The recurrent violent conflict in Plateau North Senatorial District is as a result of unresolved indigene and settlers' conflict.	44(13.1)	42(12.5)	122(36.1)	105(31.3)	22(6.6)	335
The violent conflict in Plateau North Senatorial District is due to political/economy exclusion by some aggrieved parties.	46(23.7)	158(47.2)	59(17.6)	48(14.3)	24(7.2)	335
Mean Percentage	21.2	30.1	21.2	25.7	4.6	

Key: SA=Strongly agree; A=Agree; U=Undecided; D=Disagree; SD=Strongly Disagree

Figure 1 and Table 4 present complementary insights from both the qualitative and quantitative data. Interview participants identified four primary dimensions of the violent conflicts in Plateau North Senatorial District: religious-based, ethnic-based, political-based, and resource-based factors.

Some informant noted:

I can also say they have interest in our farm produce because they end up harvesting the crops before destroying the farms. By my understanding, the violent conflict is obviously borne out of religious and ethnic wars (KII 1, 2, & 4). The nature of violent conflict in this community is purely a religious attack (KII 2, IDI 3 & 5).

When further asked whether the conflict was driven by political or economic competition, a participant responded:

Which political position? Who will give them the political position? If it is that one, they know they cannot win. It is purely a fight over land, as others have said (KII 6). To add to what others have said, it is a dispute over land grabbing and also the economic resources of the land. Since they do not own the land, their main focus of the fight now is to capture it (IDI 1, KII 2).

Regarding the religious identity aspect of the conflict, some IDI participants expressed:

Participant 2: Yes, it has a religious identity. Some of them say it is in their religion to conquer the infidels and take over their lands, so they feel they are advancing their religion. **Participant 5:** We are Christians and they are Muslims, so the conflict will definitely have a religious identity.

Quantitative data supports these insights as follows. A majority of respondents (57%) disagreed that violent conflict in Plateau North Senatorial District is carried out by both indigenous and non-indigenous militia groups. Similarly, 205 respondents (61.2%) disagreed with the idea that both sides are equally involved, while a small minority (13.6%) were either uncertain or believed both groups may be involved.

Moreover, 48.4% of respondents strongly agreed that the conflict exhibits elements of group identity. An overwhelming 94.4% of participants acknowledged ethnic and identity-related elements as recurring drivers of conflict. However, when asked to define the conflict as ethnic, opinions varied: 41.2% were unsure, 27.4% affirmed it was ethnic, while 27.2% disagreed.

On the issue of unresolved tensions, 36.1% of respondents were uncertain whether unresolved conflict was responsible for recurrent violence. Meanwhile, 37.9% disagreed with the idea that conflicts between indigenes and settlers remain unresolved. Interestingly, 47.2% of respondents agreed that the exclusion of aggrieved political actors contributes to the violence, and 70.9% strongly believed this to be the case.

In summary, Table 4 reveals a weighted mean score of 20.4%, based on five conflict nature variables $[(21.2 + 30.1 + 21.2 + 25.7 + 4.6) \div 5]$, suggesting that the violent conflict manifests in multiple forms. Notably, 30.1%—the highest response above the mean—acknowledged this multidimensional nature. Furthermore, over half (51.3%) of respondents believed that the conflict has distinct features reflecting the attackers' intentions, while 25.7% disagreed, and 21.2% remained undecided.

These findings confirm that violent conflicts in Plateau North Senatorial District are multifaceted and driven by varying degrees of religious, ethnic, political, and resource-based interests. Both the qualitative and quantitative data consistently reinforce this conclusion. When religious identity is threatened or challenged in such contexts, it can disrupt spiritual values, beliefs, and affiliations, creating moral dilemmas, spiritual crises, and long-term societal divisions that span generations.

Discussion on the Nature of Violent Conflicts in Plateau North Senatorial District

The findings of this study reveal that the nature of violent conflicts in Plateau North Senatorial District is multifaceted, comprising religious-based, ethnic-based, political-based, and resource-based dimensions. Respondents indicated that both indigenous and non-indigenous militia groups may be involved in the execution of these conflicts. The conflicts also demonstrate strong elements of group identity, corroborating Wika's (2014) assertion that the nature of conflict in any locality can often be explained through identity-based and resource-based lenses.

This conclusion is reinforced by Arbath et al. (2015), who found that genetic diversity can intensify social unrest. Similarly, Nwagwu (2016) highlighted that cultural heritage syndrome and mutual distrust significantly contribute to indigene-settler discrimination. Agbiboa (2017) further argued that the colonial system of governance entrenched ethnic and religious divisions, thus exacerbating identity-based conflicts.

In alignment with these observations, Karakoc and Wang (2021) found that political regimes can exacerbate the divide between minorities and majorities, prolonging ethnic conflict. Zhang (2023) also affirmed that internal ethnic diversity and debates over national or state identity can provoke societal transformation and tension. Belge and Karako (2015) found that support for authoritarianism was lower among linguistic minorities but higher among religious minorities, revealing complex intersections of identity and governance.

The present findings also align with those of Elom (2021), who observed that ethnic political elites often deepen citizenship dilemmas by manipulating tribal and religious sentiments for political and economic gains. Anjide and Amaechi (2022) similarly confirmed that contested notions of citizenship—manifested through indigene-settler debates—are central to the conflict. Ogbuleke (2019) identified lack of political representation, marginalization, poverty, unemployment, and elite manipulation as primary drivers of conflict in Plateau State.

Similar to findings by Nyam (2017), conflict in Jos, a part of Plateau North stems from struggles over political, social, economic, religious, and ethnic interests, all of which significantly affect intergroup relationships. Ferrara (2017) linked ongoing conflict to unresolved national identity disputes, while Anthony (2014) characterized Nigeria as a deeply divided state, where political issues are contested violently along ethnic, religious, and regional lines, often hidden behind silent identity politics.

The study further confirms the prevalence of political-based and resource-based conflicts in Plateau North. Residents cited political and economic exclusion of aggrieved groups as a root cause of ongoing violence. This is consistent with Nwagwu's (2016) finding that unequal distribution of societal benefits and competition over scarce resources drive inter- and intra-communal conflicts. Agbiboa (2017) also emphasized that the recurrent violence is fueled by competition for political power and economic control. These findings are in line with those of the Peace Building Agency (2018) and Cingel & Ugwoke (2019), who found that political

and economic marginalization breed intolerance, fear, and mistrust across ethno-religious divides.

CONCLUSION, LIMITATION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study concludes that the nature of violent conflict in Plateau North Senatorial District can be classified into religion-based, ethnic-based, political-based and resource-based struggles. The system encouraged the religious, ethnic and political divisions which also paved way for wealth accumulation by the exploitation of resources. The system likewise succeeded in strengthening the dominant and minority ethno-religious community anchored on political economy that thrives in competition and group survival. Nevertheless, this study has the major limitations of a cross-sectional design and also focusing on one senatorial district even though it is the theater of violent conflicts in Plateau State.

Moving forward, the study recommended among others: resolving historical grievances to tame frustration regression crisis reoccurrence potentials for peace and positive development; intensify peaceful conflict resolution and educate the opposing groups on choosing non-violence as an option to violence; enforce boundary demarcation on farming lands and grazing areas; and also develop a tougher justice system where perpetrators are used as scapegoats. The nature of violent conflicts has implications for policy makers, academia and the citizens.

This study concludes that the nature of violent conflict in Plateau North Senatorial District can be categorized into four primary forms: religion-based, ethnic-based, political-based, and resource-based struggles. The systemic structures in place have historically reinforced religious, ethnic, and political divisions, thereby facilitating the exploitation of resources and the accumulation of wealth by certain dominant groups. These dynamics have further entrenched the marginalization of minority ethno-religious communities, exacerbating tensions through a political economy shaped by competition and group survival.

However, this study is not without limitation. The cross-sectional research design restricts the ability to assess long-term patterns or causal relationships. Additionally, the focus on only one senatorial district—though recognized as the epicentre of violent conflicts in Plateau State—limits the generalizability of the findings to other regions.

To mitigate the recurrence of violent conflicts and promote sustainable peace and development, the following recommendations are offered:

1. **Address Historical Grievances:** There is a critical need to engage in reconciliation efforts that resolve longstanding grievances, which are often the root of frustration-regression crises. Healing historical wounds can foster social cohesion and reduce conflict potential.
2. **Promote Peace Education and Dialogue:** Stakeholders should intensify efforts in peacebuilding by educating opposing groups on the benefits of non-violent approaches to conflict resolution. Encouraging mutual understanding and coexistence is essential.
3. **Implement Land Use Reforms:** The government should enforce clear boundary demarcations between farming and grazing areas to minimize land-based disputes. This will help prevent clashes between farmers and herders, which often escalate into broader conflicts.

4. Strengthen the Justice System: A robust legal framework should be established where perpetrators of violence are held accountable. Making examples of offenders through fair and transparent justice processes will serve as a deterrent to others.

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